

Combination selection method for rice breeding efficiency

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A new method of breeding was developed in which cross combinations are selected based on productivity in early generations of hybrids. The goal is to develop high-yielding varieties. In this method, crosses are made between superior lines adaptable to the climatic and soil conditions of a specific area as females, and improved lines, intersubspecies derivations, disease-resistant lines, and new high-yielding varieties as males.

The new method consists of the following steps (see figure):

In the F_2 generation, plants are transplanted at 3 hill⁻¹ in a 10-m² area, and a check variety is grown for every 4 combinations. Only those combinations with good character traits and that yield at least 90% of what the check yields are selected.

- In the F_3 generation, the same method as that for the F_2 generation is followed, but combinations with good character traits and that yield at least 80% of what the check yields are selected.
- In the F_4 generation, 1 plant is transplanted hill⁻¹ in an area of 66 m² ~100 m² for each combination, and individual plants are selected.
- In the F_5 generation, the plants selected in the F_4 generation are line-cultivated (3.3 m² line⁻¹), and lines with good productivity and traits are selected.
- In the F_6 generation, line tests, uniformity tests, and other preliminary tests are carried out with the promising lines.
- In the F_7 and subsequent generations, line tests, uniformity tests, preliminary yield tests, and comparison tests are made, and adaptability to specific agroclimatic conditions is evaluated and lines are selected.

Design for combination selection in breeding.

The advantages of the method are as follows:

- Selection of combinations can be made scientifically based on productivity and promising combinations can be adapted.

- The numbers of lines can be reduced and the field experiments carried out in smaller areas with less labor.
- The effect of selection is very high because a choice is made with only the relevant fixed plants.

4. Accurate observations of plants and lines are possible because selection was made only from combinations of highly productive populations.

This technique has been applied to develop high-yielding varieties since 1983 and two new high-yielding rice varieties, Toenonbyeo 2 and Pyongyang 24, were developed successfully.

The mean yield of Toenonbyeo 2, in comparative tests from 1992 to 1994, was 9,475 kg ha⁻¹, outyielding the check by 1,852 kg ha⁻¹. The yield of this variety, under conditions of no-fertilizer application in 1995, was 8,101 kg ha⁻¹ in Rakrang District, where soil fertility is high. Its record yield under experi-

Germination rate (%) of three varieties under low-temperature conditions at Pyongyang in 1995.

Variety	Treatment 1 ^a			Treatment 2 ^b		
	6 d	12 d	18 d	3 d	6 d	9 d
Pyongyang 24	80	98	100	90	92	91
Yomju 1 (tolerant check 1)	12	96	100	100	100	100
Olbyeo 1 (tolerant check 2)	10	78	82	91	98	100

^a15/10 °C day/night temperature. ^b30/25 °C day/night temperature.

mental conditions was 11,706 kg ha⁻¹ with 120 kg ha⁻¹ of applied N.

The mean yield of Pyongyang 24 for 3 tests from 1993 to 1995 was 8,732 kg ha⁻¹, which was 1,873 kg ha⁻¹ higher than that of the check. This variety showed high yield under conditions of low-fertilizer application. It yielded

7,650 kg ha⁻¹ in 1995 in the demonstration plot in Sariwon City, with the application of 200 kg ha⁻¹ of ammonium sulfate. Its highest recorded experimental yield was 11,282 kg ha⁻¹. Pyongyang 24 is also highly tolerant of cold (see table). ■

Yield stability analysis of rice hybrids

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The stability of some promising rice hybrids released for yield and yield components (panicles plant⁻¹, spikelets panicle⁻¹, fertility, and grain weight) was studied at Mandya, Bangalore, Shimoga, Kathalagere, and Brahmavar in Karnataka. These locations represented different agroclimatic zones. Data from the 1994 wet season on five hybrids and four checks were analyzed as per the Eberhart and Russell model.

Highly significant genotype × environment interactions were observed for yield and yield components. No hybrid or check variety showed stability over the environments studied for yield. But all the hybrids showed an average performance with a regression coefficient (*bi*) equal to unity. This was mainly due to instability in the number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ and the degree of fertility.

Even though the regression coefficient deviated from unity, medium-duration hybrid IR58025A / KMR3 (KRH2) was the best performer at all the locations, except Brahmavar in coastal Karnataka. Another short-duration hybrid, IR58025A / IR9761-19-

1R (KRH1), also performed similarly, with a yield much superior to that of checks Rasi and Mangala at all locations except Brahmavar. The results from the correlation analysis between stability parameters (*bi* and *s²di*) for grain yield and yield components indicate that stability parameters in rice hybrids may be governed by different genes and gene interactions. ■

Yield system analysis in rice hybrids

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Grain yield is a complex trait that is influenced by genetically controlled physiological components. The rate of accumulation of biomass and actual yield, as well as the ratio between these two components, can determine a genotype's yielding ability. At a similar level of harvest index, increased grain yield can come from increased total biomass or increased harvest index, or increased biomass and harvest index. We therefore investigated the physiological and genetic causes of the yield superiority in rice hybrids in the 1994 wet season.

The test materials involved eight rice hybrids belonging to different maturity groups, their A, B, and R parents, and three check varieties—Jaya, IR72, and Tellahamsa. They were grown in three replications using a randomized complete block design. Observations on shoot and root dry weights at different growth stages were recorded on five random and competitive plants in each replication. Grain yield, panicle dry weight, and spikelet fertility were also recorded. Based on the observations, total biomass at different growth stages and harvest index were calculated.

Heterosis over the best check and better parent was calculated and subjected to a test of significance. Only IR58025A / Swarna, PMS3A / PR103, and IR58025A / IR32809 showed significant commercial heterosis for grain yield, total dry matter, and panicle dry weight at harvest despite a negative heterosis for spikelet fertility. These hybrids also showed heterosis for dry matter accumulation at many growth stages. IR58025A / IR52256 and IR62829A / IR53901 showed negative commercial heterosis for grain yield, harvest index, and spikelet fertility with no or very low heterosis for other growth parameters. The negative heterosis for spikelet fertility in all the hybrids clearly indicated a need to improve spikelet fertility in hybrids by